

IN-DEPTH CHARACTERIZATION AND SIMULATION APPROACH FOR THE UNDERSTANDING OF IN- AND OUTDOOR DEGRADATION OF PEROVSKITE SOLAR CELLS

Jonathan Parion^{1,2,3,4}, Amit Kumar Harit^{1,3,4}, Elias Peraticos^{5,6}, Vasiliki Paraskeva^{5,6}, Maria Hadjipanayi^{5,6}, Aranzazu Aguirre^{1,3,4}, Filip Duerinckx^{1,3,4}, Hariharsudan Sivaramakrishnan Radhakrishnan^{1,3,4}, Jef Poortmans^{1,3,4,7}, Johan Lauwaert² and Bart Vermang^{1,3,4}.

¹ Hasselt University, imo-imomec, Martelarenlaan 42, 3500 Hasselt, Belgium; ² Ghent University, Department of Electronics and Information Systems, Technology Park 126, 9052 Zwijnaarde, Belgium; ³ Imec, imo-imomec, Thor Park 8320, 3600 Genk, Belgium; ⁴ EnergyVille, imo-imomec, Thor Park 8320, 3600 Genk, Belgium; ⁵ PV Technology Laboratory, Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Cyprus, Nicosia 1678, Cyprus; ⁶ PHAETHON Centre of Excellence (CoE) for Intelligent, Efficient and Sustainable Energy Solutions, Nicosia 2109, Cyprus; ⁷ KU Leuven, Department of Electrical Engineering, Kasteelpark Arenberg 10, 3001 Leuven, Belgium

ABSTRACT: Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) have recently shown, on top of their very high power-conversion efficiency (PCE), a remarkable improvement in stability. Despite this, very few studies focus on the long-term testing of these devices. The exact mechanisms governing degradation are yet to be discovered and there is still a lack of a consensus on which accelerated tests can be used to accurately mimic stresses in real-life field deployment. To address these issues, this work uses several of the International Summit on Organic Photovoltaic Stability (ISOS) protocols, combined with an electrical characterization and simulation toolbox, to compare outdoor field testing of PSCs with indoor accelerated tests. The study reveals that long-term outdoor exposure mainly leads to the degradation of the perovskite absorber layer. On the contrary, the very popular dark thermal stress test affects the perovskite/electron transport layer (ETL) interface. It is also shown that testing thermal stability under light and under maximum power point tracking (MPPT) is the closest accelerated test to mimic outdoor exposure, with similar degradation features observed. Overall, this study highlights some of the key degradation modes occurring in PSCs, while showing the importance of diversified testing to better comprehend and improve the stability of these devices.

Keywords: Perovskite degradation, Perovskite outdoor, ISOS protocols, S-shape

1 INTRODUCTION

Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) have recently shown, on top of their very high power-conversion efficiency (PCE), a remarkable improvement in stability [1, 2]. They show the ability to succeed in several indoor accelerated degradation tests, defined by the International Summit on Organic Photovoltaic Stability (ISOS) protocols [3]. Even though this is an important step in the deployment of the perovskite technology, there is still a significant lack of validation of these results in real outdoor conditions. It is moreover unclear which indoor stability tests are the most suited to mimic degradation induced by real-life field exposure. Finally, despite the stability improvements, there is poor understanding as to the exact physical origin of the degradation.

This work aims at addressing these issues, by comparing in- and outdoor degradation of perovskite cells using electrical characterization combined with Devsim TCAD [4] simulations. More specifically, an ISOS-O2 test is performed in Nicosia, Cyprus for a duration of 5 months and compared with a 2000h-long ISOS-D2 test and an 85h-long ISOS-L2 test. The cells that are characterized in this work use a semi-transparent inverted p-i-n architecture and FAPbI₃-based perovskite deposited by blade coating. The cell stack is composed of ITO/NiO_x/perovskite/LiF/C₆₀/LiF/ITO/Ag. The NiO_x acts as a p-doped hole transport layer (HTL), and the LiF/C₆₀/LiF stack acts as a n-doped electron transport layer (ETL).

2 OUTDOOR STABILITY TESTING

The outdoor stability of a PSC was tested on the island of Cyprus for a period of 5 months, in between April and August 2025. The evolution of performance is shown in Figure 1. During that period, the cell maintains

Figure 1: IV measurement of the reference and passivated PSCs, with the main figures of performance given in the table inset. The black arrow shows a slight kink in the reference curve.

approximately 80% of its initial performance. The measurements were interrupted for a period of approximately 1 month between May and June and the sample was kept in dark storage at room temperature during that period. Interestingly, this does not seem to have affected the cell performance. The average sample temperature varied between 30°C and 50°C for the entire testing period, getting hotter during the summer months compared to spring.

In Figure 2a, IV curves taken at different stages of outdoor exposure are depicted. They show that the performance loss was mainly caused by a reduction in short-circuit current density (J_{sc}) and in fill-factor (FF), while the open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) remained stable

Figure 2: (a) IV curves taken at different dates during outdoor exposure with the solid and dashed curve respectively showing the forward and reverse scans, (b) maximum power point tracking of the device before and after outdoor exposure normalized by the end power value and (c) Capacitance versus frequency (Cf) measurements performed before and after outdoor exposure.

during the testing period. The J_{sc} loss is likely related to a deterioration of the absorber layer, as discussed further. The FF loss seems to be caused by an increased series resistance (R_s). This last one is initially already large, due to the interconnection method used in this specific sample. It is also worth mentioning that the hysteresis of the IV curve increases slightly as the cell degrades, which indicates a change in the behavior of mobile ionic charges. This is confirmed by the data shown in Figure 2(b), where the device MPP was measured for the pristine and degraded sample. Before this measurement, the device is stored in the dark for a few days in order to get to a resting state. Then, MPPT at room temperature and 1 sun irradiance is performed until a stabilized power output is reached. As observed on the Figure, the degraded device takes a significantly longer time to reach a steady-state,

while also starting at a much lower value. This highlights the role of degradation as an accelerator for perovskite transient effects: after degradation, the device takes a significantly longer time to reach its maximal power output than before. In Figure 2(c), the capacitance versus frequency (Cf) characteristic is represented before and after the ISOS-O2 test. In the $10^3 - 10^5$ Hz frequency region, where the geometric capacitance C_{geo} dominates, a clear reduction is observed after outdoor exposure. This is a sign of the perovskite layer degradation, in line with the J_{sc} drop and with results from previous works [5-7]. At frequencies below 10^2 Hz, the increase in capacitance is typically related to the movement of mobile ionic charges. These contribute to the total capacitance of the device only when the AC excitation is slow enough. In the present case, the low-frequency region is shifted to the right after outdoor exposure. Typically, such feature indicates an increase in the ionic diffusivity D_{ions} [6]. This is coherent with the larger hysteresis observed with time (Figure 2(a)) as well as with the increased transient effect (Figure 2(b)). Overall, these results indicate that the outdoor exposure of perovskite cells causes degradation of the absorbing layer, while increasing the transient behavior of the cell caused by mobile ions.

3 INDOOR STABILITY TESTING

Despite being fully representative of real-life operation of the cells and modules, outdoor tests are very long and therefore not practical for development and validation of new PSC architectures. For this reason, accelerated tests are often performed, the two most popular being ISOS-D2 (thermal stress in the dark) and ISOS-L2 (thermal stress under light and at MPPT). In this section, these tests are performed, analyzed and compared with the ISOS-O2 outdoor protocol to highlight the differences and similarities in the perovskite cell degradation.

3.1 ISOS-D2

In this test, samples are placed at 85°C and kept in the dark during 2000h. The IV curves taken before and after the test are represented in Figure 3(a). Two main contributors to the reduced performance are identified: a strong reduction of V_{oc} combined with a significant FF loss caused by the appearance of an ‘‘S-shape’’. This kind of feature is often attributed to the formation of an energy barrier at one of the perovskite/transport layer interfaces [8, 9]. To support the understanding of the S-shape origin, a Devsim TCAD [4] simulation model of the perovskite single-junction cell was created. The results obtained from this model are represented in solid lines in Figure 3(a). To obtain a good agreement with the experimental points, two parameters were varied between the pristine and degraded samples:

- The density N_t of the defect at the interface between the perovskite and the ETL layer was increased from $N_t = 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}$ to $N_t = 3 \cdot 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}$
- The mobility of electrons in the ETL layer μ_{ETL} was changed from $\mu_{ETL} = 5 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ to $\mu_{ETL} = 4 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

This confirms that the ISOS-D2 test mainly affects the perovskite/ETL interface, while leaving the perovskite bulk unchanged, at least for the blade-coated FAPbI₃-based absorber used in this work. It is worth mentioning

Figure 3: (a) Experimental (triangles) and simulated (solid lines) IV curves before and after ISOS-D2 test and (b) Capacitance versus frequency (C_f) measurements performed before and after ISOS-D2 test.

that changing HTL parameters and interface defect density instead of the ETL does not yield a similar result as in Figure 3(a). That layer is moreover less likely to deteriorate under thermal stress, as discussed in previous work [9-11]. Turning to Figure 3(b), this last hypothesis is further confirmed by the C_f measurements. They show no change in the intermediary capacitance region, contrarily to what was observed after outdoor exposure. There is also no change in the low frequency region of the capacitance, indicating no modification of the mobile ion transport properties. While the ISOS-D2 stress does not seem to be representative of the cell outdoor degradation for this specific case, it still enables to highlight the instabilities that can occur at the perovskite/ETL interface under thermal stress. Previous work on long-term outdoor exposure of perovskite cells and modules mentions the appearance of such S-shapes for some ETL compositions [9], which motivates the need for accelerated dark thermal stress tests such as ISOS-D2.

3.2 ISOS-L2

In this test, the sample is placed at 60°C under light and its maximum power point is tracked for a duration of 85h. The IV curves before and after the test are given in Figure 4(a). In this case, the effect of degradation on the IV curve is very similar to the ISOS-O2 test shown in Figure 1(a). There is a significant J_{sc} loss, related to the degradation of the perovskite absorber, as well as a FF loss

Figure 4: (a) Experimental IV curves before and after ISOS-L2 test. The solid and dashed lines represent respectively the forward and reverse scans. (b) Capacitance versus frequency (C_f) measurements performed before and after ISOS-L2 test.

caused by an increased R_s . Increased hysteresis is furthermore also observed after degradation and attributed to an increased D_{ions} after analysis of Figure 4(b). There, the same reduction in the geometric capacitance and increase in the transition of the low frequency capacitance are observed in the degraded sample, similarly to the ISOS-O2 case. It indicates a degradation of the absorber layer as well as an increase in the perovskite transient behavior. From Figure 4, it is very clear that the ISOS-L2 test leads in this case to the same type of degradation as the ISOS-O2 outdoor exposure, while being significantly faster. This is a promising result to support the use of the ISOS-L2 protocol to test the stability of perovskite cells.

4 CONCLUSION

This work investigated the stability behavior of PSCs in different testing conditions, both in- and outdoors. Outdoor exposure (ISOS-O2) of the cells leads to a degradation of the perovskite absorber and to an increase of the perovskite transient behavior. The same degradation is observed during indoor MPP tracking under light and heat conditions (ISOS-L2), though on a much shorter time scale. This poses the ISOS-L2 protocol as a solid candidate to validate PSCs stability in lab conditions. Finally, dark thermal stress (ISOS-D2) leads to the deterioration of the

perovskite/ETL interface, while leaving the absorber intact. Overall, this work clearly highlights the importance of diversified testing of PSCs. Indoor accelerated tests are useful for laboratory development and validation but need to be correctly tailored to mimic real outdoor deployment. In future steps, more emphasis should be placed on understanding the intrinsic causes of degradation. Moreover, recovery and seasonality effects are key topics to be investigated in order to further improve the stability of PSCs.

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